

1 **Influence of key operational parameters on biohydrogen production from fruit and**
2 **vegetable waste via lactate-driven dark fermentation**

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26 **Abstract**

27 This study aims at investigating the influence of operational parameters on biohydrogen
28 production from fruit-vegetable waste (FVW) via lactate-driven dark fermentation.
29 Mesophilic batch fermentations were conducted at different pH (5.5, 6.0, 6.5, 7.0, and non-
30 controlled), total solids (TS) contents (5, 7, and 9%) and initial cell biomass concentrations
31 (18, 180, and 1800 mg VSS/L). Higher hydrogen yields and rates were attained with more
32 neutral pH values and low TS concentrations, whereas higher biomass densities enabled
33 higher production rates and avoided wide variations in hydrogen production. A marked
34 lactate accumulation (still at neutral pH) in the fermentation broth was closely associated
35 with hydrogen inhibition. In contrast, enhanced hydrogen productions matched with much
36 lower lactate accumulations (even it was negligible in some fermentations) along with the
37 acetate and butyrate co-production but not with carbohydrates removal. At pH 7, 5% TS, and
38 1800 mg VSS/L, 49.5 NmL-H₂/g VS_{fed} and 976.4 NmL-H₂/L-h were attained.

39

40 **Keywords:** Dark fermentation; Fruit and vegetable waste; Hydrogen production; pH effect;
41 Total solids.

42

43 **1. Introduction**

44 Nowadays, the inadequate management of fruit and vegetable waste (FVW) is a global
45 concern due to its negative social impacts, economic losses and environmental damage
46 (Ganesh et al., 2022). In the European Union, it is estimated that ≈ 21 kg of unavoidable
47 FVW are generated per person annually (De Laurentiis et al., 2018). Besides postconsumer
48 generation, FVW is also generated during its entire production chain. In line with the
49 Sustainable Development Goals 2030, the European Commission actions aimed at reducing
50 food waste generation and promoting its circularity through the Circular Bioeconomy

51 Strategy (European commission, 2020). In this context, FVW is a promising feedstock to
52 produce value-added products and renewable bioenergy through a biorefinery approach (Patel
53 et al., 2019).

54 The dark fermentation (DF) process is likely the most promising route for producing
55 renewable hydrogen from organic waste, owing to its multiple advantages such as no light
56 requirement, simple operation, relatively high energy yield, and high compatibility with other
57 biotechnologies (e.g., bioplastics-accumulating fermentation, anaerobic digestion, among
58 others) within a biorefinery scheme (Mohan et al., 2016; Chen et al., 2022). Although
59 fermentative hydrogen production from food waste (including FVW) has been previously
60 investigated, some technical limitations, such as high process instability and low hydrogen
61 production yields and rates, must be overcome for further technology scale-up. These
62 bottlenecks have been mostly associated with the excessive growth of lactic acid bacteria
63 (LAB) and consequently with an accumulation of lactate (HLac) (Pu et al., 2019; Santiago et
64 al., 2019; Im et al., 2020). However, recent studies on the DF of food waste have
65 acknowledged the possibility to effectively produce hydrogen from HLac (Gomez-Romero et
66 al., 2014; Noblecourt et al., 2018; Villanueva-Galindo and Moreno-Andrade, 2021). Lactate-
67 driven DF, herein referred to as LD-DF, relies on the cooperative associations between LAB,
68 whose main end-product is HLac, and some specialized hydrogen-producing bacteria (HPB)
69 that can metabolize HLac (Detman et al., 2021; García-Depraect et al., 2021). Harnessing the
70 interactions between LAB and lactate-utilizing HPB (LU-HPB) could enable a more practical
71 and efficient hydrogen production process (Sharmila et al., 2022). However, to the best of the
72 authors' knowledge, the LD-DF of FVW has not been systematically investigated.

73 Additionally, although it is well-known that operational parameters such as pH, total solids
74 (TS) content and microbial density concentration impact the fermentative hydrogen
75 production performance (Ramos et al., 2012; Lee et al., 2014; Moon et al., 2015; Florio et al.,

2017; Cappai et al., 2018; Ghimire et al., 2016; Ghimire et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2022), there is a knowledge gap about their impact on the LD-DF using FVW as substrate. Previous studies showed that operational pH values ranging from 5.5 to 7.0 are more conducive to hydrogen production via LD-DF, but the optimal pH is rather dependent on the substrate type, microbial structure involved, and so on (García-Depraect et al., 2021). It has been also reported that high TS contents (> 15%) might redirect the carbon flux towards HLac accumulation (Ghimire et al., 2018). Similarly, the initial cell biomass concentration can also influence the hydrogen production outcome (Das et al., 2011). It is therefore crucial to deeply understand how those operational parameters would impact the LD-DF of FVW.

The present study aims at investigating the influence of culture pH, TS content, and initial biomass concentration on the hydrogen production performance from the LD-DF of FVW. To the best of authors' knowledge, this is the first effort made to elucidate the role of such key operational parameters on the FVW-to-hydrogen bioconversion via LD-DF. The findings and discussion herein presented could help in the further development of continuous high-rate DF reactors based on lactate-utilizing, hydrogen-producing pathways, thus tackling process limitations related to the excessive proliferation of LAB.

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93 **2. Materials and methods**

94 *2.1 Inoculum and substrate*

95 The source of the inoculum herein used was digestate derived from a pilot (100 L) anaerobic
96 digester treating restaurant food waste under mesophilic conditions. The recovered digestate
97 was pretreated by heat shock at 90 °C for 20 min to irreversibly inactivate methanogens
98 (García-Depraect et al., 2022a). Likewise, the enrichment of hydrolytic/acidogenic bacteria
99 was carried out by successive culture passages according to García-Depraect et al. (2019a)
100 but using a growth medium composed of (g/L) lactose 10.0, NH₄Cl 2.4, K₂HPO₄ 2.4,

101 $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 2.5, KH_2PO_4 0.6, $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 0.15, $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 0.035. The resulting inoculum
102 harbored bacteria (such as LAB and LU-HPB) able to perform the LD-DF (García-Depraect
103 et al., 2022a). On the other hand, the fresh fruits and vegetables utilized for mimicking FVW
104 were purchased from a local marketplace. The composition of FVW was adapted from
105 Abubackara et al. (2019) and consisted of banana 14.5, eggplant 12.8, carrot 9.7, tomato 8.4,
106 cucumber 7.5, onion 7.1, radish 6.5, potato 6.2, capsicum 5.7, apple 5.3, cabbage 4.7, grape
107 3.1, orange 3.1, lemon 2.7, and pumpkin 2.4% (w/w). Prior to use, the substrate was blended
108 with an electrical blender (Sammic, XM-32, Azkoitia, Spain) to reduce its particle size and to
109 get a homogenous FVW slurry. No additional tap water was required during blending. The
110 FVW was then collected in 1L plastic bags and frozen at $-20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to avoid any deterioration.
111 The physicochemical properties of the substrate are presented and discussed in section 3.1.

112

113 *2.2 Experimental set-up and operational conditions*

114 A series of batch tests was carried out to investigate the influence of pH, TS content and
115 initial cell biomass concentration on the performance of LD-DF of FVW. All fermentation
116 assays were conducted in two identical 1.25-L custom-made fermenters with a working
117 volume of 0.7 L. Each fermenter was equipped with a pH controller (BSV Electronic S. L.,
118 EVopH-P5, Spain), a pH electrode (BSV Electronic S. L., HO35-BSV01, Spain), a liquid and
119 a gas sampling port, and a custom-made biogas-flow meter operating under the liquid
120 displacement principle (see Supplementary material).

121 The effect of pH on the performance of LD-DF of FVW was investigated by
122 controlling the operational pH at 5.5, 6.0, 6.5 and 7.0, which have been found to be
123 conducive for the LD-DF (García-Depraect et al., 2021). A set of fermentations with no pH
124 control was also carried out. The initial pH of the culture broth was 4.6, while the operational
125 pH was adjusted and controlled at the target set-point by adding 6 N NaOH (or 3 N HCl if

126 needed) with an accuracy of ± 0.1 . All fermentations devoted to investigating the effect of pH
127 were performed with an initial biomass concentration of 18 mg volatile suspended solids
128 (VSS)/L and 5% TS. After the determination of the optimal pH for hydrogen production, a
129 second series of batch tests aimed at evaluating the impact of the initial TS concentration on
130 process performance was conducted. Such fermentations were carried out at an initial TS
131 content of 5, 7 and 9%, with a constant biomass concentration of 18 mg VSS/L and a fixed
132 pH of 7. It should be noted that an initial TS of 9% implied the use of undiluted FVW.
133 Finally, the influence of the initial cell biomass concentration was ascertained by testing three
134 different concentrations, i.e., 18, 180, and 1800 mg VSS/L. VSS was used as a proxy of
135 biomass concentration and the lower value of 18 mg VSS/L was the average initial biomass
136 concentration at which the experiments done to study the effect of pH and TS content were
137 carried out, thus 180 and 1800 mg VSS/L represented a 10 and 100 fold biomass increment,
138 respectively. In such fermentations, the pH and TS content were set at 7 and 5%,
139 respectively. See Supplementary material for a detailed summary of operational conditions
140 and corresponding initial substrate concentrations and initial food-to-microorganism (F/M)
141 ratios.

142 The fermenters were placed in a controlled-temperature room set at 37 ± 1 °C,
143 magnetically agitated at ~300 rpm, and sealed under air atmosphere. Tap water was used to
144 adjust the desired TS content, while fermenters were inoculated with 10% (v/v) of a fresh
145 hydrogenogenic inoculum. The preparation of the inoculum was different depending on the
146 condition tested. Thus, the inoculum preserved by refrigeration (4 °C) was reactivated before
147 each use via two successive subculture passages for the assessment of the influence of pH
148 and TS content. Briefly, an aliquot of 0.1 L of the refrigerated inoculum was cultivated for 19
149 h at 37 ± 1 °C, ~150 rpm, with no pH control, in a closed air atmosphere using a 2.1-L
150 fermenter (1 L working volume) and the defined mineral growth medium previously

151 described in section 2.1. Then, the resulting biomass was harvested from the culture broth by
152 centrifugation (10000 rpm for 10 min) and grown for 17 h under similar conditions to obtain
153 a fresh and active hydrogenogenic microbial community.

154 The inocula employed in the tests aiming at evaluating the influence of biomass
155 concentration on the LD-DF process were taken from a steady state continuous
156 hydrogenogenic culture to ensure an identical metabolic state among the different biomass
157 concentrations tested. The continuous fermentation was conducted in a 3-L Biostat-A
158 fermentor (Sartorius Stedim, Spain) with a working volume of 2 L and equipped with an
159 automated control system (Sartorius stedim biotech Biostat A). Mechanical agitation was set
160 at 300 rpm, while pH was controlled at 5.5 ± 0.05 by adding 3 N NaOH and temperature at
161 35 ± 0.5 °C. The fermenter was inoculated with refrigerated inoculum at 10% v/v. Following
162 a 24 h batch culture, the feeding regime was switched to a continuous mode, keeping a
163 constant hydraulic retention time (HRT) of 12 h and an organic loading rate (OLR) of 180 g
164 chemical oxygen demand (COD)/L-d. A pseudo-steady state was defined when hydrogen
165 productivities recorded during at least 3 consecutive HRTs remained within $\pm 10\%$. Biomass
166 concentration was estimated by means of a correlation curve between VSS and optical
167 density (OD). The culture broth was diluted or concentrated (by centrifugation at 10000 rpm
168 for 10 min) depending on the initial biomass concentration targeted, using the mineral
169 medium described in section 2.1 but without any carbon source.

170 All operational conditions were tested in duplicate, and the fermentation time was 48
171 h (corresponding to the period of time when the cumulative hydrogen production plateaued).
172 Liquid and gaseous samples were taken and analyzed periodically throughout the
173 fermentation. The key performance indicators of the process included the hydrogen yield,
174 maximum volumetric hydrogen production rate (VHPR), hydrogen content in the acidogenic
175 off-gas, as well as the removal efficiency of volatile solids (VS) and total carbohydrates, and

176 the profile of organic acids and the acidification degree. The kinetics of hydrogen production
177 obtained using the modified Gompertz model were also included as a process performance
178 indicator, as shown in section 2.5.

179

180 *2.4 Analytical techniques*

181 Total carbohydrates content was analyzed using the phenol-sulfuric method, while protein
182 content was determined by total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN) analysis using a nitrogen-to-protein
183 factor of 6.25. Likewise, pH and the concentration of COD, VS and TS were measured
184 according to standard methods (APHA, 2005). Lipid content was measured according to the
185 PNTNAG-006 SERIDA fat protocol. The elemental composition analysis (C, H, O, N, S) of
186 the substrate was performed by an elemental analyzer (EA Flash 2000, Thermo Fisher
187 Scientific) equipped with a thermal conductivity detector (TCD) and a Mettler Toledo XP6
188 microbalance. Helium was used as a carrier (140 mL/min) and reference gas (100 ml/min)
189 coupled with oxygen (250 ml/min) at 900 °C furnace temperature for C, H, N, and S, while
190 helium was used as a carrier (130 mL/min) and reference gas (100 mL/min) at 1060 °C
191 furnace temperature for O measurement. On the other hand, OD was measured at 600 nm
192 using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (BMG LABTECH, SPECTROstar Nano, Germany). The
193 concentrations of organic acids, including formate (HFor), acetate (HAc), iso-butyrate (i-
194 HBu), butyrate (HBu), propionate (HPr), HLac, iso-valerate (i-HVal), valerate (HVal), iso-
195 caproate (i-HCa), hexanoate (HHex) and heptanoate (HHep), were analyzed by high-
196 performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) using a Waters alliance model e2695
197 (Massachusetts, USA) equipped with a Waters Alliance 2998 PDA UV-Vis detector
198 (Massachusetts, USA) set at 210 nm, a IR detector for ethanol measurement, and a Thermo
199 scientific Carbohydrate H⁺ 8µm HyperREZ XP column (England, UK). The column
200 temperature was set at 75 °C, while the mobile phase was composed of 25 mM H₂SO₄ at a

201 flow rate of 0.7 mL/min. Sodium L-lactate (Sigma-Aldrich part number 71718, USA) and an
 202 organic acids mix (Sigma-Aldrich CRM46975, USA) were employed as standards for the
 203 quantification of organic acids. The composition of the gas phase was determined by gas
 204 chromatography (GC) using a Varian CP-3800 GC-TCD (PaloAlto, USA), as reported
 205 elsewhere (García-Depraect et al., 2022b). The volume of acidogenic-off gas was normalized
 206 to 0 °C and 1 atm.

207

208 2.5 Data analysis

209 Hydrogen production kinetics were analyzed using the modified Gompertz model (Eq. 1)
 210 previously described by Ramos et al. (2012), where, $H(t)$ represents the total amount of
 211 hydrogen (in NmL) produced at time t (h), H_{max} represents the maximal amount (in NmL) of
 212 hydrogen produced, R_{max} is the maximum hydrogen production rate (in mL/h), and λ stands
 213 for the lag time (in h). Each experimental condition was tested in duplicate, and the plotted
 214 data corresponds to the average and standard deviation recorded. The acidification degree
 215 was calculated according to Eq. 2, where COD eq. is the net sum of COD equivalent (in g/L)
 216 of all the organic acids measured at the end of fermentation and $TCOD_{FVW}$ is the total COD
 217 concentration (in g/L) of the FVW fed. Finally, a COD mass balance analysis was performed
 218 according to Eq. 3. COD equivalent for biomass was estimated as 5% of the total COD of the
 219 influent (García-Depraect et al., 2019b).

$$220 \quad H(t) = H_{max} * \exp \left[-\exp \left(\frac{2.71828 * R_{max} (\lambda - t)}{H_{max}} + 1 \right) \right] \quad (1)$$

$$221 \quad \text{Acidification degree (\%)} = \frac{\text{COD eq.}}{TCOD_{FVW}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

$$222 \quad \text{Total initial COD} = COD_{\text{organic acids}} + COD_{\text{residual sugars}} + COD_{H_2} + COD_{\text{biomass}} + COD_{\text{Not determined}} \quad (3)$$

223

224 3. Results and discussion

225 3.1 Physicochemical characterization of the FVW

226 Physicochemical features of the feedstock such as the content of carbohydrates, nitrogen,
227 lipids, etc., are among the most important factors governing the performance of the DF
228 process. The FVW utilized herein was characterized in detail and the results are shown in
229 Table 1. The FVW exhibited a low pH of 4.6, which implies the need of using an alkaline
230 additive such as sodium hydroxide to maintain the operational pH at suitable values (higher
231 than 5.5 in most cases) for hydrogen production (Habashy et al., 2021). The FVW had a high
232 organic matter concentration, with an associated total COD concentration of ~ 111.5 g/L, of
233 which 75.7% was found to be in a solubilized form. This indicated that most organic matter
234 in the FVW was readily available to microorganisms. Indeed, the VS/TS ratio accounted for
235 94%, while the total carbohydrates content was 78.9 ± 2.9 g/L. Thus, hydrolysis was not
236 likely the rate limiting step in the production of hydrogen during DF. As expected, the lipid
237 content was low (less than 1.5%), discarding any need for a delipidation pretreatment or DF
238 inhibition issues associated with the accumulation of lipids in the culture broth (Alibardi and
239 Cossu, 2016; Tarazona et al., 2022). In this context, the C/N ratio accounted for 31.6 ± 0.5 ,
240 which agrees with the literature reporting acceptable hydrogen productions at C/N ratios
241 between 21 and 45 (Gomez-Romero et al., 2014; Rangel et al., 2021). The ash content was on
242 average closed to 6%, suggesting the presence of essential minerals in the simulated FVW
243 used. Indeed, this study did not require to supplement the DF process with any external
244 (micro)nutrient to achieve a high hydrogen production performance (as discussed in section
245 3.2). Finally, it should be noted that although FVW is heterogenous in nature, the
246 physicochemical characterization of the FVW herein used as feedstock grossly agrees with
247 data reported in the literature: an acidic, carbohydrate-rich, readily fermentable substrate with
248 a low lipids level, which represents an excellent feedstock for fermentation-based biorefinery
249 processes (Gomez-Romero et al., 2014).

250

251 3.2 Effect of pH on the LD-DF of FVW

252 The operational pH exerted a markedly impact on both the extent and rate of hydrogen
253 production (Figure 1, Table 2). The final cumulative hydrogen production increased with
254 increasing the operational pH from 1897.5 ± 370.4 NmL/L at pH 5.5 up to 3443.1 ± 46.4
255 NmL/L at pH 7 (Table 2). Such an improved hydrogen production response according to the
256 increasing operational pH values agrees with previous studies reported in literature (Dareioli
257 et al., 2014; García-Depraect et al., 2019a). As expected, no hydrogen production was
258 observed under non-controlled pH conditions due to the low pH prevailing during the
259 fermentation process, which dropped from 4.6 down to 3.4, highlighting the need for a pH
260 control system. At pH of 5.5, the hydrogen yield averaged 41.5 ± 8.3 NmL/g VS added, and
261 increased by 15.4, 43.6 and 76.4% when the pH was kept constant at 6, 6.5 and 7,
262 respectively (Table 2). Higher pH values also resulted in a slightly higher hydrogen content
263 in the acidogenic off-gas, rising from 41.4 ± 0.4 to $49.7 \pm 1.2\%$. In contrast, the removal
264 efficiencies for VS were not significantly affected by the operational pH, reaching values
265 between 49.3 ± 0.5 and $54.6 \pm 1.5\%$, except for fermentations carried out without pH control
266 ($16.2 \pm 4.2\%$). The removal of carbohydrates ranged from 74.3 ± 1.3 to $82.4 \pm 0.5\%$ for all
267 pH conditions tested. Additionally, no clear relationship between hydrogen production and
268 the carbohydrates removal efficiency was observed, which implies that the hydrogen
269 production efficiency cannot be explained merely by the consumption of carbohydrates.

270 Table 2 shows that the modified Gompertz model adequately represented the
271 experimental data with correlations coefficients (R^2) higher than 0.99, although the diauxic
272 hydrogen production observed required the use of the model with two consecutive steps. It
273 was observed that the higher the pH, the lower the lag phase, which ranged between 6.3 and
274 8.0 h, pointing out the easily fermentable nature of FVW. A higher operational pH resulted in
275 enhanced VHPRs, thus the highest VHPR of 535.7 ± 10.1 NmL H₂/L-h was obtained at pH 7.

276 That operational condition exhibited a diauxic behavior in hydrogen production with a second
277 VHPR of 262.4 ± 146.5 NmL H₂/L-h. Indeed, a diauxic hydrogen production was also
278 observed for pH 5.5 and pH 6. The occurrence of different metabolic pathways for hydrogen
279 production could explain the diauxic hydrogen production behavior herein recorded, as
280 previously discussed by An et al. (2018).

281 The main organic acids identified in the culture broth were HLac, HFor, HAc, HBU,
282 and HPr regardless of the pH condition (Figure 2). No measurable amounts of ethanol were
283 detected for all pH conditions tested, likely due to the operational conditions and biocatalyst
284 used. Non-controlled pH conditions resulted in a marked accumulation of HLac of up to 18.3
285 ± 0.04 g/L followed by HAc (9.2 ± 0.2 g/L), which suggests that heterolactic fermentation
286 became dominant (Dareioti et al., 2014). Extreme acidic conditions also enabled HPr-type
287 fermentation with up to 4 g HPr/L. Contrarily, at a fixed pH of 5.5, the concentration of HLac
288 began to increase during the first 10 h, peaking at 7.1 ± 0.3 g/L at 24 h of cultivation and
289 thereafter it was totally consumed after 32 h of fermentation. Interestingly, relative low levels
290 of HLac in the culture broth matched with the formation of HAc and HBU. A gradual
291 accumulation of HLac during an early stage of fermentation and its further metabolization
292 accompanied by the production of HAc and HBU was also observed at pH 6, 6.5 and 7
293 (Figure 2). Notably, HFor was rapidly accumulated in the fermentation broth and re-
294 consumed during the first 4–8 h of cultivation regardless of the pH conditions. Another
295 observation is that HPr was accumulated, mainly during the stationary phase of hydrogen
296 production, for pH 6, 6.5, and 7, but not for pH 5.5. In general, the more neutral operational
297 pHs not only enabled a higher hydrogen production but also a higher recovery of carboxylic
298 acids (see Figure 2f), sustaining acidification degrees of 26.1 ± 1.5 , 39.6 ± 2.8 , 49.3 ± 0.2 ,
299 and 72.9 ± 0.9 at pH 5.5, 6, 6.5, and 7, respectively. According to the global COD mass
300 balance, 0.2–4.1% and 12.8–18.6% of the total COD of the substrate were diverted to

301 hydrogen and residual sugars depending on the pH tested, considering that biomass growth
302 accounted for 5% of the total influent COD. The recovery of COD accounted for 52.0–97.9%
303 (see Supplementary material).

304 Culture pH is one of the most important operational parameters in the DF process due
305 to its role in shaping microbial communities and their metabolic activities (Tian et al., 2019;
306 Habashy et al., 2021). According to Eqns. 4 to 6, HLac can be metabolized into hydrogen and
307 HAc or HBu depending on the prevailing pathway (García-Depraect et al., 2021). Thus, the
308 fact that HLac always remained at relatively low levels, while hydrogen is produced as the
309 concentration of HAc and HBu increased, strongly suggested the occurrence of HLac-
310 utilizing, hydrogen-producing pathways (Noblecourt et al., 2018; García-Depraect et al.,
311 2021; Villanueva-Galindo and Moreno-Andrade, 2021). The hydrogen production
312 performance during LD-DF relies on the balance between LAB and LU-HPB, which is
313 indeed influenced by the operational pH (García-Depraect et al., 2019a; Fuess et al., 2019;
314 Detman et al., 2021). It has been argued that LAB and LU-HPB can coexist via lactate cross-
315 feeding interactions (García-Depraect et al., 2021). In this context, it is also worth to mention
316 that all DF tests were carried out using a seed inoculum harboring LAB and LU-HPB, which
317 jointly are metabolically able to sustain LD-DF (García-Depraect et al., 2022a). It was
318 therefore suggested that pH-neutral conditions supported an improved balance and syntrophy
319 between LAB and LU-HPB (Jung et al., 2021; Kim et al., 2022). However, although, as
320 mentioned before, there was no clear trend in the efficiency of carbohydrates removal and the
321 amount of hydrogen produced, some hydrogen might have been formed from carbohydrates.
322 Furthermore, it must be stressed that heterolactic fermentation and/or homoacetogenic
323 pathway might also have contributed to the high levels of HAc herein measured (Dareioti et
324 al., 2014). Further molecular analyses can help to better understand the carbon flow.

328

329 *3.3 Effect of initial TS content on the LD-DF of FVW*

330 The TS content of FVW was also found to impact both the extent and rate of hydrogen
331 production (Table 2, Figure 3). Particularly, the hydrogen production efficiency severely
332 decreased with increasing the TS content from 3443.1 ± 46.4 NmL/L at 5% TS to $264.7 \pm$
333 64.0 NmL/L at 9% TS (4.1 to 0.2% of the initial COD), with associated hydrogen yields
334 ranging from 3.3 ± 0.8 to 73.2 ± 1.0 NmL H₂/g VS fed (Table 2). The hydrogen content in the
335 biogas peaked at 49.7 ± 4.1 , 67.7 ± 0.1 and $52.5 \pm 4.6\%$ at a TS content of 5, 7, and 9%,
336 respectively. The lowest VS removal efficiency of 31.4% was achieved at a TS concentration
337 of 9%, which was 34.7 and 73.9% lower than those recorded at 7 and 5% TS, respectively.
338 Finally, the removal efficiency of carbohydrates ranged from 72.7 ± 2.7 to $77.7 \pm 1.0\%$,
339 regardless of the TS content tested, highlighting the fact that hydrogen production via LD-DF
340 and the consumption of carbohydrates were uncoupled. However, carbohydrates were still
341 needed to provide HLac as further hydrogen precursor (García-Depraect et al., 2021). The
342 enhancement in hydrogen production performance herein found when decreasing the TS
343 content in the substrate was also endorsed kinetically. Thus, the lag phase ranged between 6.3
344 and 13.2 h, while the VHPR varied between 102.9 ± 36.4 and 685.7 ± 161.6 NmL H₂/L-h. A
345 TS content of 5% sustained the shortest adaptation time, the highest hydrogen yield, and a
346 VHPR similar to that computed at 7% TS (Table 2).

347 The major organic acids detected in the fermentation broth included HLac, HAac,
348 HBU, HPr and HFor, and their accumulation dynamics depended on the TS content (Figure
349 4). There was no evidence of ethanol-type fermentation regardless of the condition tested. A
350 slightly accumulation of HPr (2.6–2.9 g/L) at the end of the fermentation was only observed

351 at 5 and 7% TS contents, likely because those conditions enabled hydrogen production. The
352 organic acids profile at 5% TS was discussed in section 3.2. An accumulation of HLac (up to
353 33.0 ± 4.5 g/L) and HAc (up to 7.9 ± 1.1 g/L), but not of HBU that remained at 0.8 ± 0.3 g/L
354 at the end of the process, was observed at 9% TS (the condition supporting the lowest
355 hydrogen production). HLac and HAc accumulated up to 11.2 ± 1.0 g/L and 8.7 ± 0.02 ,
356 respectively, at 7% TS, but HLac was gradually consumed to 9.0 ± 0.1 during the
357 acceleration phase of hydrogen production. At first sight, this HLac accumulation along with
358 the effective hydrogen production recorded at 7% TS seems to be contradictory to the LD-DF
359 pathway. However, the fact that HLac can be produced but also consumed simultaneously
360 may explain the behavior observed for HLac at 7% TS, which also tended to decrease at the
361 end of fermentation and its maximum concentration in the culture broth was comparatively
362 much lower than that measured at 9% TS. The acidification degree at 5% TS was the highest
363 ($72.9 \pm 0.9\%$), while a TS content of 7% supported the lowest acidification degree ($28.4 \pm$
364 0.9%), followed by 9% TS ($42.4 \pm 3.4\%$). This highlighted the relevance of the prevailing
365 metabolic fluxes, especially the HLac flux, during LD-DF. In this context, the TS content of
366 FVW may shape microbial populations and cause a shift in metabolic pathways (Chen et al.,
367 2022). It is well recognized that the efficient bioconversion of complex particulate substrates
368 to hydrogen needs a suitable balance between hydrolytic and fermentative bacteria. It has
369 been previously hypothesized that the presence of particulate material may alter the balance
370 between LAB and LU-HPB during LD-DF, leading to higher LAB activities at higher TS
371 contents, while lower TS contents may boost the activity of LU-HPB (García-Depraect et al.,
372 2019c), thus explaining why low TS contents were ascertained in this study as more
373 conducive to hydrogen production.

374

375 *3.4 Effect of initial biomass concentration on the LD-DF of FVW*

376 The role of initial cell biomass concentration on the performance of LD-DF of FVW was
377 investigated in a third series of batch tests at different biomass concentrations (i.e., 18, 180,
378 and 1800 mg VSS/L). Interestingly, the inoculum concentration did not exert a clear effect on
379 the extent of hydrogen production but on its rate (Figure 5, Table 2). The average cumulative
380 hydrogen production varied between 1980.1 and 2726.2 NmL/L, with corresponding average
381 hydrogen yields of 49.5–60.4 NmL/g VS fed. The highest hydrogen production was attained
382 at 18 mg VSS/L (Table 2). The hydrogen content in the acidogenic off-gas ranged from 45.8
383 to 65.5%. It must be highlighted that a biomass concentration of 18 mg VSS/L resulted in a
384 larger variation in the volume of hydrogen produced compared to that in the other tested
385 conditions, likely due to the low initial microbial density in the fermenter. The VS and
386 carbohydrates removal efficiencies were close to 50 and 84%, respectively, regardless of the
387 initial microbial density (Table 2). Finally, the lag phase in hydrogen production decreased
388 from 9.5 to 6.8 h as the biomass concentration increased, while VHPRs of 717.8 ± 57.9 , 1035
389 ± 10.1 and 976.4 ± 48.7 NmL H₂/L-h were attained at 18, 180 and 1800 mg VSS/L,
390 respectively.

391 Considering that 10- and 100-fold biomass increments showed very similar VHPRs,
392 and the slightly lower hydrogen yield observed in the former assays (Table 2), it is suggested
393 to maintain a high concentration of desirable bacteria in LD-DF systems to produce hydrogen
394 more efficiently. However, more organic matter may be devoted to biomass production rather
395 than hydrogen production at too high cell concentrations (Das et al., 2011; Wu et al., 2012). It
396 should be also noted that the DF process is impacted not only by the initial biomass
397 concentration but also by its physical state (lag, log, or stationary); where a rapidly dividing
398 state may sustain superior performances (Das et al., 2011). The seed herein employed as the
399 workhorse was obtained from a fermenter producing hydrogen continuously and stably from
400 a lactose-based mineral medium. The performance of the seed reactor in terms of hydrogen

401 productivity, biomass concentration and profile of organic acids is shown in the
402 Supplementary material. It must be noted that the larger biomass concentration entailed a low
403 F/M ratio (see Supplementary material), and therefore, the increase in VHPR at larger
404 microbial densities could be explained by the high number of microorganisms that may make
405 faster the bioconversion.

406 HAc, HLac, HFor, HPr and HBu were the main organic acids identified during the
407 assessment of the influence of the biomass concentration (Figure 6). HAc was the most
408 dominant intermediate regardless of the biomass concentration, similarly to the previous
409 fermentations displaying high hydrogen production performances (see sections 3.2 and 3.3).
410 For all conditions tested, no ethanol was detected throughout the fermentation. HPr was
411 accumulated, especially at the late stage of fermentation, at concentrations ~ 1.0 g/L
412 regardless of the biomass concentration tested. Significant concentrations of HLac were also
413 observed, mainly at early stages of fermentation, although this organic acid remained at very
414 low levels during the late stages of fermentation independent of the condition tested. A
415 concurrent HAc and HBu accumulation during HLac uptake was also recorded. Thus, the
416 metabolic patterns observed reinforced the idea that, under the conditions studied, the main
417 route for hydrogen production involved the consumption of HLac. However, it is difficult to
418 determine the exact contribution of different HLac-utilizing, hydrogen-producing pathways
419 since HLac could have been produced and consumed to different extents. Overall, the
420 empirical findings observed in this assay provided a strong indication that FVW was an
421 effective substrate for hydrogen production despite the prevalence of HLac in the
422 fermentation broth, which strongly suggests the presence of HLac producers, showing the
423 advantageous LD-DF process herein proposed.

424

425 3.5 Significance of the study and perspectives

426 One of the main bottlenecks of the DF process is the impairment in hydrogen production
427 caused by the overgrowth of LAB. LAB are commonly seen as unfavourable bacteria to DF
428 due to substrate competition, excretion of bacteriocins, and because HLac is not associated
429 with hydrogen production. Recently, hydrogen production from HLac, herein referred to as
430 LD-DF has been reported as an alternative pathway to cope with LAB associated issues
431 (García-Depraect et al., 2021). Indeed, there is evidence of the occurrence of HLac-utilizing,
432 hydrogen-producing pathways using food waste as substrate (Gomez-Romero et al., 2014;
433 Noblecourt et al., 2018; Villanueva-Galindo and Moreno-Andrade, 2021). The novelty of the
434 present study lies in conducting systematic research to evaluate the effect of pH, TS content,
435 and initial biomass concentration on the performance of LD-DF of FVW. Those are key
436 operational parameters extensively studied (especially pH and TS content) via conventional
437 DF but not for LD-DF. Hydrogen is typically produced directly from carbohydrates via
438 acetic- and butyric-type fermentation. In contrast, HLac (formed from carbohydrates) is
439 hydrogen precursor during LD-DF. From an ecological perspective, LD-DF would benefit
440 from LAB through a cooperative association with LU-HPB. Such a syntrophy is absent when
441 the microbial structure governing the DF process does not have the potential to metabolize
442 HLac into hydrogen, which often results in the accumulation of HLac in the fermentation
443 broth and hydrogen inhibition. LAB commonly thrive and proliferate in DF reactors, on the
444 one hand, because of their ubiquitous nature (for instance they are found in many cases as
445 part of the indigenous microbiota of substrate) and, on the other hand, because they can grow
446 well in the process and environmental conditions at which DF reactors are operated and also
447 may outcompete HPB due to their more rapid substrate uptake and/or higher growth rate
448 using complex substrates (García-Depraect et al., 2021). Substrates and inocula are
449 commonly subjected to pretreatments (e.g., alkali, acid, temperature shock) as a measure to
450 avoid the over proliferation of LAB (Capson-Tojo et al., 2016). From a practical process

451 point of view, LD-DF enables to avoid any pretreatment, thus leading to a more cost-effective
452 process.

453 The results herein presented indicated that LD-DF is a feasible fermentation route to
454 produce hydrogen from FVW, and the operational parameters tested govern both hydrogen
455 production and its associated metabolic pathways. Furthermore, the potential of the LD-DF
456 process herein proposed could be measured by comparing the hydrogen production yields and
457 rates recorded in this study with those already reported for FVW in literature. Studies on the
458 valorization of FVW into hydrogen via DF are still scarce. Gomez-Romero et al. (2014)
459 reported a VHPR of 234.1 NmL H₂/L-h with an associated hydrogen yield of 142 NmL H₂/g
460 VS fed using FVW. Abubackara et al. (2019) reported a hydrogen yield of 27.2 and 20.8
461 NmL H₂/g VS fed from the thermophilic DF of autoclave and non-autoclaved FVW,
462 respectively. The present study achieved a hydrogen yield of \approx 50 NmL H₂/g VS fed but an
463 outstanding VHPR of 976.4 NmL/L-h. That unprecedented hydrogen production rate shows the
464 potential advantage of the LD-DF to be further optimized. Future studies should investigate
465 the continuous hydrogen production and related microbial communities, with a special
466 emphasis on selecting suitable operational and environmental parameters to boost the HLac-
467 to-hydrogen bioconversion.

468 **4. Conclusions**

469 This study revealed that the FVW-to-hydrogen bioconversion via LD-DF is strongly
470 impacted by culture pH, TS content, and initial biomass concentration. Superior hydrogen
471 productions were associated with HLac consumption along with HAc and HBu production
472 rather than carbohydrates consumption. Findings indicated that a more neutral pH along with
473 a higher initial microbial density and lower solid contents in the substrate mediated superior
474 hydrogen production rates. The highest VHPR of 976 NmL/L-h was achieved at pH 7, 5% TS

475 and 1800 mg VSS/L. Overall, the LD-DF process represents an effective route to produce
476 hydrogen from FVW, while tackling LAB inhibition issues.

477

478 E-supplementary data of this work can be found in online version of the paper.

479

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488

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645

646 **Figure captions:**

647 **Figure 1.** Time course of cumulative hydrogen production at different operational pH
648 values. Continuous lines represent the predicted data obtained from the modified
649 Gompertz model.

650

651 **Figure 2.** Time course of organic acids at different operational pH values. a) non-
652 controlled, b) pH 5.5, c) pH 6.0, d) pH 6.5, e) pH 7.0, and f) sum of COD equivalent for
653 each organic acid measured at the end of the fermentation.

654

655 **Figure 3.** Time course of cumulative hydrogen production at different TS
656 concentrations. Continuous lines represent the predicted data obtained from the
657 modified Gompertz model.

658

659 **Figure 4.** Time course of organic acids at different TS contents. a) 5%, b) 7%, c) 9%,
660 and d) sum of COD equivalent for each organic acid measured at the end of the
661 fermentation.

662

663 **Figure 5.** Time course of cumulative hydrogen production at different inoculum
664 concentrations. Continuous lines represent the predicted data obtained from the
665 modified Gompertz model.

666

667 **Figure 6.** Time course of organic acids at different inoculum concentrations. a) 18, b)
668 180, c) 1800 mg VSS/L, and d) sum of COD equivalent for each organic acid measured
669 at the end of the fermentation.

Table 1. Physicochemical characterization of the FVW.

Parameter	Aver. \pm S.D.
pH	4.6 \pm 0.1
Total COD, g/L	111.5 \pm 5.1
Soluble COD, g/L	84.5 \pm 0.3
TKN, g N/kg	2.4 \pm 0.1
Phosphorus, g/L	3.7
Total solids, g/L	95.2 \pm 2.0
Volatile solids, g/L	89.5 \pm 1.5
Total carbohydrates, % dry basis	82.8 \pm 3.0
Protein, % dry basis	15.5 \pm 0.7
Lipids, % dry basis	1.2
Ash, % dry basis	5.9 \pm 0.6
Elemental carbon, %	44.2 \pm 0.4
Elemental hydrogen, %	5.7 \pm 0.2
Elemental oxygen, %	41.7 \pm 0.3
Elemental nitrogen, %	1.4 \pm 0.0

672 **Table 2.** Summary of operational performance indicators at different operational pH, initial TS content and initial biomass concentration.

Parameter	Production NmL H ₂ /L	Yield NmL H ₂ /g VS fed	VHPR NmL H ₂ /L- h	^a H ₂ %	VS removal %	^b CHO removal %	<i>t</i> h	<i>R</i> _{max} NmL H ₂ /h	<i>P</i> NmL H ₂	<i>R</i> ²	
^c NC	0	0	0	0	16.2 ± 4.2	77.7 ± 2.0	-	-	-	-	
pH, 5% TS and 18 mg VSS/L initial biomass concentration	5.5	1897.5 ± 370.4	41.5 ± 8.3	300.8 ± 47.5/ 197.4 ± 46.8	41.4 ± 0.4	51.2 ± 1.9	74.3 ± 1.3	8.0 ± 0.1,	210.5 ± 33.2/ 138.2 ± 32.8	1027.2 ± 172.6, 1326.7 ± 262.4	0.9997
	6.0	2162.0 ± 428.5	47.9 ± 10.6	322.7 ± 23.3/ 336.1 ± 42.3	43.2 ± 3.6	53.8 ± 3.5	78.1 ± 0.8	7.4 ± 0.4	225.9 ± 16.3/ 235.3 ± 29.6	1510.0 ± 299.9	0.9900
	6.5	2742.4 ± 114.7	59.6 ± 2.7	450.0 ± 40.4	45.3 ± 5.0	49.3 ± 0.5	82.4 ± 0.5	6.8 ± 0.2	315.0 ± 28.3	1914.0 ± 75.7	0.9919
	^d 7.0	3443.1 ± 46.4	73.2 ± 1.0	535.7 ± 10.1/ 262.4 ± 146.5	49.7 ± 1.2	54.6 ± 1.5	77.7 ± 1.5	6.3 ± 0.0	375.0 ± 7.1/ 183.7 ± 102.5	2457.2 ± 118.7	0.9943
	TS content (%), pH 7.0 and 18 mg VSS/L initial biomass concentration	7	4051.3 ± 3.0	61.9 ± 0.2	685.7 ± 161.6	67.7 ± 0.1	42.3 ± 2.5	77.3 ± 2.1	12.8 ± 0.1	480.0 ± 113.1	2846.7 ± 63.7
9		264.7 ± 64.0	3.3 ± 0.8	102.9 ± 36.4	52.5 ± 4.6	31.4 ± 0.7	72.7 ± 2.7	13.2 ± 0.4	72.0 ± 25.5	126.4 ± 37.4	0.9908
Initial cell biomass concentration (mg VSS/L), pH 7.0 and 5% TS	18	2726.2 ± 683.8	60.4 ± 15.8	717.8 ± 57.9	65.5 ± 10.7	46.4 ± 4.1	84.8 ± 0.5	9.5 ± 0.1	502.4 ± 40.5	1871.9 ± 402.0	0.9945
	180	1980.1 ± 251.7	41.2 ± 4.6	1035.7 ± 10.1	52.9 ± 0.3	48.7 ± 1.0	84.0 ± 0.8	8.5 ± 0.1	725.0 ± 7.1	1381.0 ± 169.9	0.9939
	1800	2329.7 ± 191.3	49.5 ± 4.7	976.4 ± 48.7	45.8 ± 0.4	51.1 ± 1.8	84.6 ± 0.2	6.8 ± 0.1	683.5 ± 34.1	1627.6 ± 131.0	0.9971

673 **Note:** ^a peak hydrogen concentration; ^b CHO: carbohydrates; ^c NC: non-controlled pH; ^d This condition also represented 5% TS.

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Fig. 1

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Fig. 2

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Fig. 3

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Fig. 4

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Fig. 5

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Fig. 6